

Analysis of ionomer properties in cathodic catalyst layers prepared by electro spray

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The ionomer phase is responsible for the proton conductivity of the catalyst layer (CL) in a proton-exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) electrode [1,2]. Apart from proton conductivity, it has an impact on other properties of the layer, like thickness, porosity, electrochemical surface area (ECSA), oxygen transport properties, wettability, electronic conductivity, and mechanical strength, which affect water management and catalytic activity in the CL. The behavior of the ionomer phase depends on intrinsic properties, like composition, molecular weight and ion-exchange capability, as well as morphology, 3D distribution, and interaction with the Pt/C particles within the CL. The deposition method used to prepare the CL has, therefore, an important impact on the ionomer phase, and, with it, on the performance and durability of the PEMFC.

Among CL deposition methods, the electro spray of catalyst inks gives rise to layers characterized by superhydrophobic macropores, due to ionomer and catalyst particles deposited under the influence of a strong electric field [3]. Such morphology provides interesting properties to PEMFC electrodes, like enhanced water transport capability, low ionic resistivity, and high durability. Standard testing of PEMFC with electro spray CL in cathode has shown above 20% increased peak power density due to lower voltage losses at intermediate and high current density.

In this communication, a study is presented of CLs prepared by electro spray with different ionomer concentrations (ionomer to carbon ratio, I/C). The electro sprayed CLs are characterized by microscopy techniques, nanoindentation, and single cell PEMFC testing, and their properties compared with those of CLs prepared by standard decal methods.

Figure 1: a) Electro spray deposition set-up. b) and c) SEM images of the surface of CL prepared by electro spray (b), and spray (c). d) Polarization curves comparing PEMFC with electro spray cathodic CL and with commercial CL.

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